

Qualitative and quantitative study of protozoans in Bennetura reservoir from Omerga Taluka M.S. India

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Abstract

The present 'study of qualitative and quantitative of protozoans in Bennetura reservoir from omerga taluka m.s. India' The work carried out during a year June 2021 to May 2022. Location of Bennetura 76°-27"-40"Longitude and 17°-47"-40"Latitudes. It's manmade earthen reservoir having maximum height 13.38 meter, catchment area is 79.58sq.kms and capacity of live storage 11.47 mm³, full tank level water 10.30m..Its nine villages in command and reservoir is constructed year of completion in 1984. The Bennetura reservoir distance from omerga to dam is about 18 km. The water is used for irrigation, agricultural, sugar factories, domestic activity, drinking and fishery purpose. The study of qualitative and quantitative protozoans is very important because this may be help to analysis the environmental degradation. The analysis revealed that there were seven genera belong to zooplankton group protozoans. The zooplankton group protozoans population in reservoir ranged between 12 to 23 nos./lit. It's maximum protozoans in month of summer season 23nos./lit.in month of may and minimum population in month of monsoon season 12nos./lit.in month of August in Bennetura reservoir from omerga taluka.

Keywords : Quality of water, protozoans, Bennetura reservoir

Introduction

Water is the greatest gift of nature without which the survival of animals and plants is impossible. We use water in our daily life more frequently. The planet earth is the only planet with the presence of liquid water and it is covered with almost 71% of water and most of the earth's water is in oceans which covers almost 97%of the earth's water which is salt water and the rest of the water.. 3% is fresh water which is present in other forms like glaciers, polar ice caps, rivers, lakes, streams, reservoir etc. In which the water bodies are extensively used by people for several purpose. All the activities have been resulted in altering the physico-chemical nature and quality of water in the reservoir which ultimately affects the diversity and density of biomass in the water bodies. The bio indication of water quality is an emerging and important aspect of environmental assessment. Zooplanktons play a crucial role not only converting plant food to animal food but also themselves as sources of food for higher organisms especially in the freshwater ecosystem. The availability and adaptation depends on the surrounding environmental factors. The freshwater communities i.e. zooplankton macrophytes and macro Invertebrates are sensitive to environment factors. Zooplankton is considered as one of the most important linkage in Aquatic food chain and play a major role in energy transfers. Affect their total aquatic bio data. Zooplankton increases the biological productivity of the water bodies. A number of

like Ghosh (1919)Govind (1963), Diwan(1989), S.L.Bhalkare& G.T.Rathod (2010). Zooplankton diversity and their Ecology greatly contribute to as understanding of the basic mayor and general economy of aquatic habitats (Sigh& Mahajan 1987). Protozoans the part of zooplankton is an informal term for a group of single celled eukaryotes either free living or parasitic that feed on organic matter such as other microorganism or organic tissue & debris. Protozoan represents a large number of species and has been used as indicator of water quality. This study investigated the qualitative and quantitative group of protozoans in Bennetura reservoir from omerga taluka.

Material and method

The study of qualitative and quantitative group of protozoans in Bennetura reservoir from omerga taluka m.s. India during a year June 2021 to May 2022.. The protozoans sampling collected using zooplankton net made of bolting nylon cloth. The sample were fixed 4% formaldehyde solution and preserved for preliminary identification of zooplankton, standard monographs and compound binocular microscope used. Edmondson (1959), Sonali (1980), Barish (1992), APHA(1975), Kodarkar (1998), Dhonpathi (2000) and has further been confirmed with the kind help from experts at. Zoologist.

Result and Discussions

The study of qualitative and quantitative analysis of protozoans in Bennetura reservoir from omerga taluka m.s. India revealed that there were seven genera belong to

zooplankton(Protozoans) table no.1The reservoir shown ranged between 12 to 23 zooplankton population of protozoans in nos./lit. in 12 months.

Table no. 1 The Qualitative and Quantitative Genera of Protozoans Monthly density (nos./Lit.)June 2021 to May 2022

Group	S	Genera	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Total nos./lit.12Mon
Protozoans	1	Amoeba Sps.	03	02	01	02	04	03	02	02	03	02	03	03	30
	2	Bursariatun catella	01	01	02	02	01	02	03	04	02	03	02	03	25
	3	Ceratiurn hirudinella	02	01	01	03	02	03	02	02	03	03	02	02	26
	4	Cyphoderia ampulla	03	02	02	02	02	01	02	01	02	02	02	03	24
	5	Euglenia Sps.	04	03	02	03	04	03	04	03	04	04	03	04	41
	6	Paramecium Sps.	04	03	02	03	02	03	04	02	04	03	04	04	38
	7	Volvox aureus	04	03	02	02	04	02	04	03	04	04	04	04	40
Season			Monsoon season				Winter Season				Summer Season				
Total nos./Lit. average			21		1	17	19	1		17	22	2		23	

The maximum population density of protozoans was observed in months of June to September 2021 of monsoon season 12 to 23 nos./lit. The higher productivity of protozoans in summer is due to turbid water. The minimum population

density of protozoans was observed in months of February to May 2022 of summer season 20 to 23 nos./lit. The June to September 2021 rain fall may be due to dilution effect in Bennetura reservoir.

Graph 1. The Qualitative and Quantitative Genera of Protozoans Average density (nos./Lit.)June 2021 to May 2022

Graph 2. The Qualitative and Quantitative Genera of Protozoans Monthly density (nos./Lit.) June 2021 to May 2022

The present result shows that number/lit. Protozoan's population in June 21 to May 22 comprise total seven genera belonging to Euglena sps. 41 nos./12lit. in twelve months species dominant over any other genera than Volvaxaureus 40 no's /12lit. in twelve months, Paramecium spa. 38 no's /12 lit.in twelve

months, Amoeba spa. 30 nos./12 lit. in twelve months, Ceratiumhiradinella spa. 26 nos./12 lit. in twelve months, Bursariatruncatella 25 nos./12lit.in twelve months ,and Cyphoderia ampulla is 24nos./12lit.in twelve months observed. For most of the time is

Plates: Protozoans

throughout at a year population of protozoans was maximum in summer season while minimum in the months of monsoon season. The high population of protozoans was observed in Bennetura reservoir. The occurrence of certain member than were tolerant to organic pollution in Bennetura reservoir indicate the polluted nature of water bodies in Bennetura manmade reservoir from Omerga Taluka.

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